

MODELLING PROBLEMS OF DAMAGE AND FRACTURE OF NOTCHED FIBRE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The Kortschot, Spearing, Beaumont model of notch-tip damage in carbon fibre/epoxy laminates has had some success at predicting the early stages of damage growth in glass fibre/epoxy laminates under monotonic and cyclic loading. However, the model is not universally applicable in its present form to the propagation of damage in glass/epoxy, particularly in high cycle fatigue. This deficiency in the model can be attributed to the effects of the transverse (90°) ply crack on the breakage of glass fibre within the 0° ply neighbour. Although the K-S-B model takes into account the effect of transverse ply cracking on changes in laminate compliance, it does not consider the stress concentration effect of the transverse ply crack on the localised tensile stress in the fibres of the adjacent 0° ply.

KEYWORDS: modelling, damage, fracture, cracks, carbon fibre, glass fibre, epoxy

INTRODUCTION

An important difference between carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy is in the degree of anisotropy. Whilst the ratio of longitudinal modulus to transverse modulus of a unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminate is between 15 and 20, that of glass/epoxy is closer to 3 or 4. This means for a cross-ply glass/epoxy laminate, the 90° ply carries a greater share of the applied tensile load than would carbon fibre. Thus, the relative magnitude of the stress increment transferred into a longitudinal 0° ply adjacent to a transverse ply crack (tpc) in the 90° ply neighbour is greater for the glass/epoxy.

The Kortschot, Spearing and Beaumont model is of damage accumulation in the vicinity of a notch-tip. This physical model is based on the identification by direct observation of matrix-dominated cracking processes in cross-ply and multi-directional carbon/epoxy laminates under monotonic [1,2] and cyclic loading [3,4]. This paper assesses the applicability of the K-S-B model to a wider range of composite material systems, notably glass/epoxy laminates, in terms of:

- (1) monotonic and cyclic tensile loading
- (2) damage, applied stress, and load cycles
- (3) transverse ply thickness
- (4) terminal damage-state, fracture stress, and post-fatigue strength.

K-S-B MODEL

The K-S-B model is based on the direct observation and assessment of matrix-dominated cracking in the vicinity of a notch-tip: a split in the 0° ply; a delamination at the 0°/90° interface, roughly triangular in shape; and a crack in the transverse or 90° ply, (see Kortschot and Beaumont [1,2] and Spearing and Beaumont [3,4]). Under monotonic or cyclic loading, the damage zone doesn't change its shape, it simply grows in size. The extent of damage can be characterised by a straightforward measurement of split length and angle at the tip of the split and delamination crack which forms the triangle, known as the delamination angle. This is physically sound for cross-ply carbon/epoxy laminates.

The fracture stress of the damaged laminate depends on competition between these mechanisms which, on the one hand, reduce the stress concentration of the notch by notch-tip blunting, and on the other by reducing the tensile strength of the load bearing 0° ply close to the notch-tip. In carbon/epoxy, the notch-tip blunting mechanisms dominate and the post-fatigue strength of the laminate actually goes up. This may not be the case in other fibre-matrix systems.

COMPOSITE SYSTEMS, SPECIMEN DESIGN

Composite Materials

Glass/epoxy laminates (913G-E) were prepared by Polymeric Composites, Bristol (UK) and carbon/epoxy laminates (924C-T300) were made by Ciba-Geigy, Duxford (UK). The laminates were moulded into sheets measuring 600mm by 750mm and cured in accordance with the manufacturers specifications. Tensile tests in monotonic and cyclic loading were performed on (0/90/0), (0/90)_s, (0/90₂)_s and (0/90₄)_s laminate configurations.

Specimen Geometry

Parallel-sided tensile specimens were cut to a width of 20mm and a gauge length of 160mm using a guillotine. Two 2mm diameter holes, centres spaced 6mm apart, were drilled at the mid-section of the specimen. These holes were connected by an 8mm long central notch, cut with a diamond-coated hacksaw blade. The notch/specimen width ratio ($2a/w = 0.4$), is similar to that used by Kortschot and Beaumont [1,2] and Spearing and Beaumont [3,4]. For comparative purposes, some tests were carried out on unnotched samples.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Quasi-static Tensile Strength and Fatigue Strength

Five duplicate tensile tests were performed to determine the quasi-static fracture strength. A computer-controlled Instron 6025 screw-driven mechanical testing machine was used for this purpose at a displacement-rate of 1mm/min. Similar notched specimens were cyclically-loaded in tension using an Instron 1271 servo-hydraulic mechanical testing machine in load control with a cyclic stress ratio $R = 0.1$ at a frequency of 5Hz. Each specimen was fatigued at 80% of its quasi-static fracture strength.

Damage Observation and Assessment

Damage growth in carbon/epoxy laminates was observed using a zinc iodide penetrant dye solution and X-ray radiography. The optical properties of glass/epoxy laminates allow the direct observation of damage growth. Split length in glass/epoxy was determined by placing a micrometer against the actual surface of the specimen and from measurements taken from photographs of cracks at regular intervals. Where possible to do so, the delamination angle was calculated by assuming a triangular-shaped delamination crack, after K-S-B.

QUASI-STATIC FRACTURE STRESS MEASUREMENTS

Components of Damage

In notched glass/epoxy laminates, as with carbon/epoxy, the mechanisms of cracking are:

- (1) splitting within the 0° ply
- (2) transverse ply (90°) matrix cracking
- (3) delamination of the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface
- (4) fibre fracture within the 0° ply.

Damage Growth

Damage growth in glass/epoxy with increasing load and ply thickness is shown in Fig. 1.

(0/90/0) glass/epoxy

A split initiates at the notch-tip and propagates under increasing load. A fine dispersion of closely-spaced transverse ply cracks also develops in the vicinity of the notch-tip. At stresses approaching the fracture stress of the laminate, fibres in the longitudinal 0° ply snap sequentially at the notch-tip. By these processes, the notch-tip damage zone grows by a series of localised fibre breaks until the laminate finally separates into two pieces.

(0/90)_s glass/epoxy

The appearance and development of damage are similar to that observed of the (0/90/0) laminate. Having either a single or double transverse ply within the laminate, fibre fracture is not dominant but part of the overall failure process. The relationship between applied tensile stress and normalised split length (l/a) is one where split length scales with the square of applied stress, as found and modelled by Korschot and Beaumont for carbon/epoxy.

(0/90₂)_s glass/epoxy

A split initiates at an applied stress close to the fracture stress. Transverse cracks in the quadruple-layered 90° ply are prominent and widely-spaced. At final fracture, damage propagates from the tip of the notch to the edge of the specimen in a series of sub-failures with fibres snapping in the 0° ply. This effectively increases stably the length of the notch. A new split initiates in the 0° ply at the edges of the notch-tip crack. The notch extends by stable crack growth until the laminate fractures completely. Figure 1 indicates that fibre breaks in

the 0° ply are coincident with the plane of transverse ply cracks in the vicinity of the notch-tip. Delamination at the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface is apparent.

$(0/90_4)_s$ glass/epoxy

In this 8-layer transverse ply laminate, failure is characterised by the growth at the notch-tip of a single transverse crack only. Under increasing stress, the tpc extends towards the edge of the specimen. Close to specimen fracture, fibre breakage in the 0° ply adjacent to the notch-tip is apparent along the line of the tpc. Ultimate failure of the laminate is accompanied by delamination of the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface which initiates at the single transverse ply crack.

We observe that damage which develops in the $(0/90_2)_s$ laminate is a combination of the two modes of failure. The transverse ply thickness of the $(0/90_2)_s$ laminate represents a transition between dominating failure mechanisms.

Fracture Stress and Transverse Ply Thickness

The effect of transverse ply thickness on laminate fracture stress, where fracture stress is expressed as the average failure stress carried by the longitudinal 0° plies, is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: The effect of transverse ply thickness on notched glass/epoxy fracture stress, where fracture stress is expressed as the average stress carried by the longitudinal 0° plies

FATIGUE DAMAGE AND POST-FATIGUE STRENGTH

Components of Fatigue Damage in Glass/Epoxy

The components of damage are similar to but more extensive than observed in monotonic loading. Even in the early stages of fatigue damage, it is possible to identify and determine the delamination angle (Table 1).

Table 1: Approximate delamination angle

<i>laminate</i>	α
(0/90/0)	4°
(0/90) _s	6°
(0/90 ₂) _s	12°
(0/90 ₄) _s	40°

Fatigue Damage Growth

The extent of fatigue damage in glass/epoxy with load cycling at 80% of laminate strength depends on ply thickness (Fig. 3). The stress indicated for each specimen is based on the stress carried by the 0° plies of the laminate.

(0/90/0) glass/epoxy

Initially, fatigue damage accumulates with the characteristic pattern identified by Kortschot, Spearing and Beaumont (Fig. 3). Furthermore, an additional damage mode develops between 10K and 20K load cycles: fibres in the 0° ply at the tip of a split fracture through the thickness of that ply. This creates effectively a secondary notch at the tip of the split from which a second series of splits form. As the cross-sectional area reduces, the stress in the remaining ligament increases, which subsequently affects the split growth-rate. With additional fatigue, further splitting occurs at broken fibre bundles. In this way, random damage develops in the composite. Damage progresses from the notch-tip towards the edge of the specimen, as it does so reducing the load-carrying capacity of the laminate. At 70K load cycles, the damage has spread throughout the laminate. In one ligament of specimen, four or more groups of splits can be seen. Damage continues to propagate until catastrophic failure, in this example, at 71.3K load cycles. The development of a non-geometrical damage zone occurred between 10K and 20K load cycles.

(0/90)_s glass/epoxy

Initially, a similar pattern of damage to that reported by Kortschot, Spearing and Beaumont is observed in specimens fatigued at 340 MPa (Fig. 3). However, by 10K cycles, it is apparent that each split is made up of a multiple array of closely spaced cracks. While these cracks initiated from or near to the notch-tip, the behaviour of the specimen resembles essentially single crack growth as observed in isotropic materials. At 40K load cycles, a new split has nucleated at the tip of a bundle of fractured fibres lying in the plane of the notch. At 60K load cycles, secondary damage has grown beyond the original splits resulting in additional fibre fracture. This process continues until the weakened specimen is no longer able to support the applied load. It fails at 78.8K load cycles. Most fatigue failures occurred at approximately

Fig. 1: Sequence of X-ray pictures showing the effects of load and transverse ply thickness on damage growth in glass/epoxy

(0/90/0) glass/epoxy laminate fatigued at 330MPa.

(0/90) glass/epoxy laminate fatigued at 340MPa.

(0/90)₂ glass/epoxy laminate fatigued at 360MPa.

(0/90)₄ glass/epoxy laminate fatigued at 405MPa.

Fig. 3: Sequence of X-ray pictures showing the effects of load cycling and transverse ply thickness on damage growth in glass/epoxy

120K load cycles. In this material, damage could no longer be described in simple geometrical terms by 20 or 30K load cycles.

(0/90₂)_s glass/epoxy

Overall, damage is different to that observed in laminates having fewer transverse plies (Fig. 3). It is dominated by the development of splits and delaminations, rather than by fibre fracture. At 40K load cycles, some damage has extended across the specimen by fibre fracture but the extent of this damage is considerably less than in laminates having only one or two transverse plies. The form of damage remains predominantly one of splitting and delamination. Finally, the material fractured at 73.5K load cycles.

(0/90₄)_s glass/epoxy

The most significant feature of this damage is the absence of fibre fracture in the 0° ply prior to fatigue failure (Fig. 3). Damage develops simply as splitting at the notch-tip with delamination at the 0°/90° interface. Interaction between the delamination and transverse ply cracking plays an important part in the damage process. Failure of the specimen occurs at 9.4K load cycles and is characterised by large delaminated regions extending across the width of the specimen.

UNNOTCHED POST-FATIGUE STRENGTH

Aluminium end-tabs were bonded to 140mm wide by 300mm length plates of glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy laminates with a heat-curing resin. Each plate was cyclically-loaded in a 20-tonne Losenhauserwerk servo-hydraulic mechanical test machine.

Glass/epoxy laminates were cyclically-loaded to 50% of their ultimate strength of 600MPa. Laminates were fatigued in load control up to 10K load cycles at 5Hz and a stress ratio $R = 0.2$. To begin with, the carbon/epoxy laminates were also fatigued at 50% of their fracture strength but due to a large number of laminate failures below 10K cycles, the maximum cyclic stress was reduced to 720MPa or 35% of ultimate.

Parallel-sided specimens for determining post-fatigue tensile strength were cut and ground from these fatigue-damaged plates to a size of roughly 6mm wide by 100mm length. To ensure failure within the gauge length, these specimens were further waisted to a width of 2mm at the mid-plane using a 125mm diameter grinding wheel. Thirty specimens were prepared for each fatigue loading history and laminate. The post-fatigue tensile tests were performed using an Instron 6025 screw-driven mechanical testing machine, as described in section 4.1.

Unnotched Post-Fatigue Tensile Strength

For comparative purposes, the post-fatigue strength was calculated by assuming the applied load is carried essentially by the longitudinal plies only. This method of normalisation is based on the premise that the laminate close to failure has a multiple array of matrix cracks in the transverse ply. Thus, the applied load is carried principally by the 0° ply.

Fig. 4 Unnotched monotonic tensile strength of glass/epoxy with transverse ply thickness

Fig. 5 Unnotched tensile strength of glass/epoxy with transverse ply thickness before and after 10K cycles

Fig. 6 Unnotched tensile strength of carbon/epoxy with transverse ply thickness before and after 10K cycles

Glass/Epoxy laminates

The monotonic tensile strength of the longitudinal ply decreases continuously as the thickness of the transverse ply increases (Fig. 4). The error bars correspond to one standard deviation. The fracture stress of the (0/90/0) laminate is approximately 20% greater than that of the (0/90₄)_s laminate. This variation in strength is sensitive to the density or spacing of the transverse ply crack which in turn depends on thickness of the 90° layer. By 10K cycles, fatigue has little effect on the residual strength of (0/90₂)_s and (0/90₄)_s laminates, while the residual strength of (0/90/0) and of (0/90)_s laminates has decreased by 18% and 8%, respectively, (Fig. 5). The implication is that for laminates containing a single or double transverse ply, fatigue results in rapid degradation of the laminate strength. The transition occurs for laminates having three transverse plies, or a thickness of 0.45mm .

Recall that in the notched laminate having a single or double central 90° ply, fatigue loading resulted in massive, progressive fibre-fracture prior to ultimate failure. In monotonic loading, fibre breakage was evident only at loads close to ultimate failure. In laminates containing four and eight central transverse plies, the dominant mode of failure was by delamination. It is the absence of delamination and notch-tip blunting at the 0°/90° interface of the single or double transverse ply which is responsible for the strength degradation.

Carbon/Epoxy laminates

The effect of transverse ply thickness on the monotonic tensile strength of carbon/epoxy is the opposite to that observed for glass/epoxy, where the fracture stress of (0/90₄)_s is approximately 20% greater than the (0/90/0) laminate. The general effect of load cycling is shown in Fig. 6. This is the mirror-image of the pattern observed for glass/epoxy. Cracks form in the transverse ply. Fatigue damage results in an increase in laminate compliance as the density of transverse cracks increases. The post-fatigue strength of the carbon/epoxy is relatively unaffected since the strength of the longitudinal ply is essentially retained.

FINAL REMARKS

The most significant difference between the carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy laminate containing a notch is that the latter fails in fatigue whereas the post-fatigue strength of the former actually goes up. In fatigue of unnotched glass/epoxy, there are significant reductions in the residual strength of the laminate containing a single or double transverse ply. Delamination at the 0°/90° interface of the 4 and 8-transverse ply laminate, however, results in crack-tip blunting effects. The result is that strength of the thicker laminate becomes independent of transverse ply thickness because of these blunting effects. The relation between unnotched post-fatigue strength and transverse ply thickness of carbon/epoxy is the mirror-image due to the difference in the degree of anisotropy.

The Kortschot, Spearing, Beaumont model which has considerable success with carbon/epoxy has limited application to glass/epoxy due to the development of complex damage modes in the vicinity of a notch. The evidence presented here indicates that the breakage of glass fibre which results from transverse ply cracking is not confined to the interlaminar region but develops through the thickness of the ply. This substantially compromises the load-carrying capability of the laminate. Emphasis must shift, therefore, from modelling the geometry of

the damage zone to include in the model a component for the strength degradation of the 0° ply and by taking into account the thickness of the transverse ply, also.

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